

Table S1: Patient Characteristics and Primary Outcome Measures.

	Mean (SD, min-max)		Missing values ^b	t-test (t _{df} , p, d) ^c		correlations (r _{df} , p) ^d	
	MD ^a	CBP		MD/CBP	MD vs CBP	MD	MPI: pain severity
n	96	109					
n _{women} ^e	51	65	0/0	X ² ₁ =0.64, p=.43	d=0.15		
Age	51.71 (14.74, 18-86)	49.05 (11.91, 18-68)	0/0	t _{182.58} =1.41, p=.16	d=0.20	r ₉₆ =-.24, p=.02	r ₉₆ =-.22, p=.03
MPI: pain severity	2.39 (1.70, 0-6)	3.30 (1.16, 0-6)	0/2	t_{165.27}=-4.43, p<.001 ***	d=0.64		
MPI: interference	2.31 (1.76, 0-5.8)	2.86 (1.36, 0-6)	0/2	t _{178.05} =-2.48, p=.01	d=0.35	r₉₆=-.89, p<.001 ***	
MPI: affective distress	2.06 (1.20, 0-4.67)	2.56 (1.32, 0-5.33)	0/3	t _{202.83} =-2.88, p=.004	d=0.40	r₉₆=-.41, p<.001 ***	r₉₆=-.56, p<.001 ***
MPI: support	3.14 (1.96, 0-6)	2.99 (1.78, 0-6)	2/9	t _{193.32} =0.56, p=.58	d=0.08	r₉₆=-.48, p<.001 ***	r₉₆=-.49, p<.001 ***
MPI: self-control	4.28 (1.03, 1.33-6)	3.95 (1.17, 1-6)	0/3	t _{202.99} =2.10, p=.04	d=0.29	r₉₆=-.38, p<.001 **	r₉₆=-.48, p<.001 ***
SF-12: physical health	36.54 (12.00, 17.24-55.87)	37.81 (9.07, 19.38-60.45)	3/10	t _{175.52} =-0.85, p=.40	d=0.12	r₉₆=-.69, p<.001 ***	r₉₆=-.76, p<.001 ***
SF-12: mental health	47.05 (8.31, 22.63-65.51)	45.29 (11.67, 19.36-65.24)	3/10	t _{194.80} =1.25, p=.21	d=0.17	r ₉₆ =-.16, p=.12	r ₉₆ =-.22, p=.03
CES-D	16.16 (9.80, 0-41)	19.54 (11.55, 0-59)	3/16	t _{202.72} =-2.27, p=.02	d=0.31	r₉₆=-.45, p<.001 ***	r₉₆=-.56, p<.001 ***
CPG ^f	2.5 (0-4, 0-4)	3 (2-3, 1-4)	7/25	W=4564, p=.11	d=0.23	r₉₆=-.67, p<.001 ***	r₉₆=-.68, p<.001 ***
Pain duration ^g	6 (5-6, 1-6)	6 (5-6, 2-6)	11/1	W=4759, p=.19	d=0.18	r₉₆=-.51, p<.001 ***	r₉₆=-.51, p<.001 ***
PES: sensory	14.29 (4.79, 10-31)	17.46 (6.51, 10-40)	7/9	t_{196.96}=-4.00, p<.001 ***	d=0.55	r₉₆=-.60, p<.001 ***	r₉₆=-.61, p<.001 ***
PES: affective	23.70 (9.65, 14-56)	30.32 (8.78, 14-53)	0/13	t_{193.55}=-5.11, p<.001 ***	d=0.57	r₉₆=-.76, p<.001 ***	r₉₆=-.78, p<.001 ***

Abbreviations: MPI: West Haven-Yale Multidimensional Pain Inventory^{1, 2}; SF-12: Short Form Health Survey^{3, 4}; CES-D: Center for Epidemiological Studies-Depression scale^{5, 6}; CPG: Chronic Pain Grade^{7, 8}; PES: Pain Experience Scale^{9, 10}; MD: Mitochondrial Disease; CBP: Chronic Back Pain; SD: standard deviation; min: minimum; max: maximum df: degrees of freedom;

^a For patient diagnoses and separate analysis see Table S2

^b Missing values were imputed using the MICE package in R, applying predictive mean matching for numeric variables and a proportional odds model for ordered variables.

^c Exact p-values are given, significant effects after correction for multiple comparisons using the Bonferroni correction are shown in bold with *p<.00357, **p<.00071, ***p<.00007.

^d Exact p-values are given, significant correlations after correction for multiple comparisons using the Bonferroni correction are shown in bold with *p<.00417, **p<.00083, ***p<.00008.

^e Number of female subjects in the sample. For the comparison of the frequency of male versus female gender between MD and CBP a X² test was conducted.

^f Raw values are shown as median and interquartile range. To compare pain chronicity (CPG) between groups, a Wilcox test was conducted and Spearman rank correlations were employed to calculate the relationship with other variables.

^g Pain duration was assessed as an ordered variable: 1: <1 month 2: <½ year 3: <1 year 4: <2 years 5: <5 years 6: >5 years. Raw values are shown as median and interquartile range. Wilcox tests and Spearman rank correlations were conducted for pain duration.

Table S2: Comparison of Subgroups of Patients with Mitochondrial Disease with Patients with Chronic Back Pain.

	CBP		CPEO			CPEOplus				LHON				MELAS				MM				OTHER				
	<i>n</i>	<i>n</i>	χ^2_1	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>n</i>	χ^2_1	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>n</i>	χ^2_1	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>n</i>	χ^2_1	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>n</i>	χ^2_1	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>n</i>	χ^2_1	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	
<i>n</i> _n	109	27				25				9				7				14				14				
<i>n</i> _{women}	65	14	0.27	0.61	0.17	13	0.22	0.64	0.17	3	1.40	0.24	0.59	5	0.05	0.83	0.28	8	0.00	1.00	0.06	8	0.00	1.00	0.06	
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i> (<i>df</i>)	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i> (<i>df</i>)	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i> (<i>df</i>)	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i> (<i>df</i>)	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i> (<i>df</i>)	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i> (<i>df</i>)	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	
Age	49.05 (11.91)	54.11 (13.22)	1.82 (37.16)	0.077	0.42	56.28 (13.31)	-2.05 (28.2)	0.05	0.61	30.22 (9.34)	-5.68 (10.28)	<.001 ***	1.60	44.43 (12.09)	-0.98 (6.77)	0.361	0.39	61.86 (10.26)	4.31 (17.82)	<.001 ***	1.09	46.21 (11.9)	-0.84 (16.53)	0.414	0.24	
MPI: pain severity	3.30 (1.16)	2.21 (1.59)	-3.33 (33.19)	0.002 *	0.86	2.48 (1.92)	-0.79 (29.79)	0.435	0.22	0.44 (0.69)	-11.2 (12.19)	<.001 ***	2.51	3.19 (1.07)	-0.26 (6.95)	0.805	0.09	3.1 (1.22)	-0.59 (16.22)	0.563	0.17	2.69 (1.78)	-1.24 (14.46)	0.234	0.49	
MPI: interference	2.86 (1.36)	2.01 (1.61)	-2.52 (35.83)	0.016	0.6	2.54 (1.92)	-1.05 (35.63)	0.302	0.23	0.42 (1.01)	-6.75 (10.56)	<.001 ***	1.82	2.67 (1.45)	-0.34 (6.71)	0.743	0.14	3.14 (1.48)	0.66 (15.97)	0.516	0.2	2.68 (1.8)	-0.37 (14.98)	0.717	0.13	
MPI: affective distress	2.56 (1.32)	1.65 (1.21)	-3.42 (42.63)	0.001 *	0.7	2.25 (1.33)	1.24 (38.88)	0.223	0.26	2.11 (0.97)	-1.3 (10.61)	0.222	0.35	1.86 (1.27)	-1.42 (6.86)	0.2	0.53	2.29 (1.37)	-0.71 (16.27)	0.485	0.21	2.31 (0.7)	-1.12 (27.07)	0.271	0.2	
MPI: support	2.99 (1.78)	2.91 (1.87)	-0.2 (38.43)	0.844	0.04	3.44 (1.59)	0.42 (38.79)	0.68	0.09	1.15 (2.19)	-2.46 (8.89)	0.037	1.02	3.9 (2.18)	1.08 (6.52)	0.317	0.51	3.71 (1.8)	1.41 (16.42)	0.176	0.41	3.36 (2.03)	0.64 (15.66)	0.531	0.2	
MPI: self-control	3.95 (1.17)	4.53 (1.03)	2.54 (44.27)	0.015	0.5	4.05 (1.05)	-0.64 (29.96)	0.526	0.17	4.33 (0.99)	1.09 (9.95)	0.3	0.33	4.81 (1.05)	2.07 (6.99)	0.077	0.74	4.24 (0.9)	1.07 (19.12)	0.298	0.25	3.93 (1.11)	-0.08 (16.92)	0.937	0.02	
SF-12: physical health	37.81 (9.07)	38.71 (11.03)	0.39 (35.2)	0.696	0.1	36.1 (12.59)	-0.25 (42.37)	0.803	0.05	51.23 (3.94)	8.53 (16.31)	<.001 ***	1.52	35.18 (10.7)	-0.63 (6.57)	0.547	0.29	28.24 (9.04)	-3.72 (16.54)	0.002 *	1.05	32.64 (11.05)	-1.68 (15.33)	0.114	0.56	
SF-12: mental health	45.29 (11.67)	48.49 (8.17)	1.66 (55.51)	0.103	0.29	44.73 (9.5)	-1.05 (39.85)	0.299	0.21	47.82 (5.37)	1.2 (15.28)	0.248	0.22	48.32 (9.38)	0.82 (7.25)	0.441	0.26	45.84 (10.21)	0.19 (17.67)	0.853	0.05	48.47 (4.78)	1.88 (37.8)	0.068	0.29	
CES-D	19.54 (11.55)	15.22 (9.68)	-1.99 (46.22)	0.052	0.39	17.12 (10.08)	-2.05 (28.2)	0.05	0.61	10.67 (11.1)	-2.3 (9.49)	0.046	0.77	13.57 (4.39)	-2.99 (12.38)	0.011	0.53	18.5 (10.62)	-0.34 (17.21)	0.737	0.09	18.71 (9.39)	-0.3 (18.46)	0.766	0.07	
PES: sensory	17.46 (6.51)	13.89 (4.19)	-3.5 (61.13)	0.001 *	0.58	13 (3.7)	-4.61 (63.2)	<.001 ***	0.73	10.78 (1.2)	-9.01 (65.34)	<.001 ***	1.06	14.57 (3.55)	-1.95 (8.85)	0.083	0.45	17.14 (6.64)	-0.17 (16.38)	0.869	0.05	16.64 (5.44)	-0.52 (18.14)	0.612	0.13	
PES: affective	30.32 (8.78)	23.59 (8.45)	3.67 (41.07)	0.001 *	0.77	23.08 (9.77)	-3.4 (33.47)	0.002 *	0.81	14.22 (0.67)	-18.5 (115.97)	<.001 ***	1.9	27.14 (14.38)	-0.58 (6.29)	0.583	0.35	24.93 (8.21)	-2.29 (17.06)	0.035	0.62	28.14 (10.32)	-0.76 (15.52)	0.461	0.24	
	<i>Med</i> (<i>IQR</i>)	<i>Med</i> (<i>IQR</i>)	<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Med</i> (<i>IQR</i>)	<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Med</i> (<i>IQR</i>)	<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Med</i> (<i>IQR</i>)	<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Med</i> (<i>IQR</i>)	<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Med</i> (<i>IQR</i>)	<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	
CPG	3 (2-3)	2 (0-3)	1127	0.054	0.26	3 (2-4)	1374	0.948	0.00	0 (0-0)	97	<.001 ***	0.61	2 (2-3)	348.5	0.696	0.06	3 (1-4)	806.5	0.724	0.04	3 (1-4)	811	0.696	0.06	
Pain duration ^b	6 (5-6)	6 (5-6)	1267.5	0.188	0.18	6 (4-6)	1186	0.227	0.16	5 (5-6)	330	0.053	0.26	6 (6-6)	434	0.457	0.10	6 (6-6)	816.5	0.602	0.08	6 (5-6)	725	0.717	0.06	

Subsamples were compared to patients with chronic back pain (CBP) using t-tests, Wilcox test and χ^2 test, respectively. Exact p-values are given, significant effects after correction for multiple comparisons using the Bonferroni correction are shown in bold with **p*<.00357, ***p*<.00071, ****p*<.00007

^a Number of female subjects in the sample. For the comparison of the frequency of male versus female gender between MD and CBP a χ^2 test was conducted.

^b Pain duration was assessed as an ordered variable: 1: <1 month 2: <¼ year 3: <1 year 4: <2 years 5: <5 years 6: >5 years.

Abbreviations: MPI: West Haven-Yale Multidimensional Pain Inventory; SF-12: Short Form Health Survey; CES-D: Center for Epidemiological Studies-Depression scale; CPG: Chronic Pain Grade; PES: Pain Experience Scale; CBP: Chronic back pain; CPEO: Chronic progressive external ophthalmoplegia; CPEOplus: CPEO with additional symptoms; MM: Mitochondrial myopathy; LHON: Leber's hereditary optic neuropathy; MELAS: Mitochondrial encephalopathy, lactic acidosis, and stroke-like episodes; OTHER: diagnosis with *n*≤5; SD: standard deviation; df: degrees of freedom; Med: Median; IQR: Inter quartile range;

Figure S1: Sensory-affective characteristics of pain in subgroups of patients with MD. Sensory and affective characteristics of the pain experience of subpopulations of patients with MD (CPEO: dark green; CPEOplus: turquoise; LHON: dark blue; MELAS: pink; MM: purple; OTHER: grey) and patients with CBP (black). Values are depicted as mean and standard error of the mean. The x-axis depicts how well an adjective represents the pain experience of the patients (1="not at all", 2="a little", 3="mostly", 4="exactly"). The y-axis depicts 24 different pain characteristics derived from the Pain Experience Scale. Abbreviations: CBP: Chronic back pain; CPEO: Chronic progressive external ophthalmoplegia; CPEOplus: CPEO with additional symptoms; MM: Mitochondrial myopathy; LHON: Leber's hereditary optic neuropathy; MELAS: Mitochondrial encephalopathy, lactic acidosis, and stroke-like episodes; OTHER: diagnosis with $n \leq 5$;

Figure S2: Self-reported pain treatment experience and perceived effectiveness reported by patients with MD. The number of patients that reported treatment experience are depicted on the y-axis, the type of treatment on the x-axis. Sixty-two out of 96 patients indicated to have received one or more treatments for their pain. The remaining 34 patients did not give any information (including no information on whether they had received treatment at all). Multiple answers were possible. The colour code indicates the perceived effectiveness of the respective treatment: green = treatment was perceived as effective, yellow = treatment was perceived as temporary effective, grey = treatment was perceived as not effective, red = patient did not specify perceived effectiveness of the treatment.

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